

Development of Fractional Ostrowski-Mercer Type Inequalities Involving s-Convex Function

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Abstract

This study aims to establish new generalized versions of Ostrowski's like inequalities associated with unified fractional operators, and Breckner convexity in the second sense. To accomplish this task, we derive a new fractional identity. Deploying this fractional auxiliary result and Mercer inequality for s-convexity, we construct new bounds of Ostrowski's like inequalities. Furthermore, we present some potential consequences and applications of the proposed results.

1. Introduction

The theory of convex function is a primary component in generating novel forms of existing and new inequalities in different frameworks. Convexity and its various generalizations are applied to overcome the limitations of convexity. Among the other classes of convexity, *s*-convexity has its value in the literature due to unifying the classical counterparts of convexity and containing several non-convex mappings. Now, we recall the notion of *s*-convex functions. Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be *s*-Breckner-convex function, if

$$f((1-t)a + tb) \leq (1-t)^s f(z) + t^s f(b),$$

$$t \in [0,1] \text{ and } s > 0.$$

For more detail, see [1]. Likewise, we deliver the well-known Jensen's inequality associated with Breckner-convex functions, established by Dragomir in [1]. Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be *s*-Breckner-convex function, if

$$f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i x_i\right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i^s f(x_i), \gamma_i > 0,$$

$$x_i \in [a, b] \text{ with } \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i x_i = 1. \quad (1.1)$$

Inequality (1.1) reduces to classical Jensen inequality with $s = 1$. Several generalizations and modifications of Jensen's inequality along with applications have recently been presented. For more, details, see [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Mercer [8] presented another generalization of Jensen inequality, known as Jensen-Mercer inequality, and it is beneficial to evaluate the

bounds for reversing Jensen's inequality as well. This inequality is proved in [8]. Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function and $x, y \in [a, b]$ such that $x < y$, then

$$f\left(a + b - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i x_i\right) \leq f(a) + f(b) - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i f(x_i), \gamma_i > 0, x_i \in [a, b] \text{ with } \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i x_i = 1.$$

Kian and Moslehian used the Jensen-Mercer inequality and demonstrated the Hermite Hadamard Mercer inequality in [2] as:

$$f\left(a + b - \frac{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2}{2}\right) \quad (1.2)$$

$$\leq \frac{1}{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2} \int_{\gamma_1}^{\gamma_2} f(a + b - t) dt$$

$$\leq \frac{f(a + b - \gamma_1) + f(a + b - \gamma_2)}{2}$$

$$\leq f(a) + f(b) - \frac{f(\gamma_1) + f(\gamma_2)}{2},$$

where f is a convex function on $[a, b]$. Cortez and his fellows [10] successfully developed the Jensen-Mercer inequality for *h*-convex mapping.

Let $h: (0,1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be mapping. If $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a *h* convex mapping, then

$$f\left(a + b - \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i x_i\right) \leq M[f(a) + f(b)] - \sum_{i=1}^n h(\gamma_i) f(x_i), \gamma_i > 0, x_i \in [a, b] \text{ with } \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i x_i = 1, \text{ and } M = \{\text{suph}(t): t \in (0,1)\}.$$

Moreover by specifying $h(t) = t, t^s, \frac{1}{t}, t(1-t)$ and t^{-s} , we obtain the Jensen-Mercer inequality for convex, *s* convex, Godunova Levin convex, tgs and Godunova-Levin *s*-convex mappings respectively. Through the wide

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utilization of Jensen-Mercer inequality, several new counterparts of trapezium-like inequalities have been demonstrated. Ogulmus et al [11] formulated the fractional variants of Hadamard-Maerker's like inequalities. Zhao et al[14] utilized the Caputo derivative operator to analyze trapezium Mercer-like inequalities for higher-order differentiable mapping. You et al [15] established the Hermite-Hadamard-Mercer inequalities leveraging the concept of harmonic convexity. Also, Cortez et al [12, 13] presented the parametric Mercer-type inequalities via fractional calculus and some discussed new advancements regarding Ostrowski's inequality by means of generalized fractional calculus and convexity respectively. For more detail, see [16, 17, 18, 19].

Let $f: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on the interior of I such that f' is integrable on $[a, b]$, where $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$. If $|f'(\omega)| < M$, then

$$\left| f(\omega) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(u) du \right| \leq \frac{M}{(b-a)} \left[\frac{(\omega-a)^2 + (b-\omega)^2}{2} \right]$$

holds for all $\omega \in [a, b]$. For more detail, see [20, 21, 22, 23].

Awan et al. [24] extended the notions of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and ψ -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and defined the class of ψ_k -fractional integrals as:

Definition 1.1 Let $f \in L[a, b]$ and $\psi: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ be an increasing function possessing continuous derivative ψ' . Then left and right ψ_k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals of f with respect to ψ is defined as

$$kI^{\alpha, \psi}_a f(x) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^x (\psi(x) - \psi(t))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \psi'(t) f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$kI^{\alpha, \psi}_b f(x) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_x^b (\psi(t) - \psi(x))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \psi'(t) f(t) dt, \quad x < b$$

where Γ_k is a k -gamma function In [25], authors computed the Ostrowski-Mercer type inequalities in association with differentiable convex mappings. In [26] Butt and his fellows examined the Ostrowski-Mercer-like inequalities through a unified fractional operator relying on monotone mapping. Recently, Ramzan et al [27] analyzed the conformable fractional Ostrowski-Mercer kinds inequalities with applicable analysis.

The principle motive of the current study is to investigate Ostrowski's like inequalities through a unified k -fractional operator and Mercer inequality. We split our study into three major parts, in the first section, we give the background of problems and some essential results. In the next section, we will initiate our main result by proving a new fractional unified identity, which will be beneficial to obtain the bounds of one-point quadrature schemes. Later on, some relation between

means will be presented.

2. Results and Discussion

Lemma 2.1

Suppose that a mapping $f: I = [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is differentiable on (a, b) with $b > a$. If $f' \in L_1[a, b]$, then for all $x, y_1, y_2, v \in [a, b]$ and $\alpha > 0$, the following identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v) \\ &= \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)} (\psi(t) - (x+a-v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt \\ & \quad + \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)} ((x+b-v) - \psi(t))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt, \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} & \Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v) \\ &= \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \\ & \quad - \frac{\Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{y_2 - y_1} \left\{ I^{\alpha, \psi}_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)-} (f \circ \psi)(\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + I^{\alpha, \psi}_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)+} (f \circ \psi)(\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

satisfies for $t \in [0, 1]$.

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \frac{\Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{y_2 - y_1} I^{\alpha, \psi}_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)-} (f \circ \psi)(\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)) \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)} (\psi(t) - (x+a-v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)} (f \circ \psi)(t) d(\psi(t) - (x+a-v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} dt \\ &= \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+a-y_1) \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)} (\psi(t) - (x+a-v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt, \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

and similarly, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= \frac{\Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{y_2 - y_1} I^{\alpha, \psi}_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)+} (f \circ \psi)(\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)) \\ &= \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)} ((x+b-v) - \psi(t))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt. \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

It follows from (2.2) and (2.3) that

$$\frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{y_2 - y_1} f(x+b-y_2) - I_1 - I_2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)} (\psi(t) - (x + a - v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)} ((x + b - v) - \psi(t))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t) (f' \circ \psi)(t) dt,
 \end{aligned}$$

which ends the proof.

Theorem 2.2 We assume that all the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'|$ is a s -convex function on $[a, b]$, then for all $\alpha > 0$, the following inequality satisfies for $t \in [0, 1]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 &\leq \frac{k(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)| + |f'(a)|) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_1)| + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)| \right] \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{k(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)| + |f'(b)|) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_2)| + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)| \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Through (2.1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v) \\
 &= \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+a-v)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+a-y_1)} (\psi(t_1) - (x + a - v))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t_1) (f' \circ \psi)(t_1) dt_1 \\
 &\quad + \frac{1}{y_2 - y_1} \int_{\psi^{-1}(x+b-y_2)}^{\psi^{-1}(x+b-v)} ((x + b - v) - \psi(t_2))^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \psi'(t_2) (f' \circ \psi)(t_2) dt_2. \tag{2.4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Change of the variables $s_1 = \frac{\psi(t_1) - (x+a-v)}{v-y_1}$ and $s_2 = \frac{(x+b-v) - \psi(t_2)}{y_2-v}$ and then $t = s_1 = s_2$ into (2.4), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v) \\
 &= \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| dt. \tag{2.5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $|f'|$ is a convex function on $[a, b]$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 &\leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| dt \\
 &\leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \{ |f'(x)| + |f'(a)| - [t^s |f'(y_1)| + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|] \} dt \\
 &\quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \{ |f'(x)| + |f'(b)| - [t^s |f'(y_2)| + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|] \} dt
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\leq \frac{k(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)| + |f'(a)|) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_1)| + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)| \right] \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{k(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)| + |f'(b)|) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_2)| + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)| \right] \right\},
 \end{aligned}$$

which ends the proof.

Corollary 2.3 If we set $\psi(t) = t, y_1 = a, y_2 = b$ and $v = x$ with $\alpha = k = s = 1$ in Theorem 2.2, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| f(x) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \\
 &\frac{(x-a)^2}{3(b-a)} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} |f'(a)| + |f'(x)| \right\} + \frac{(b-x)^2}{3(b-a)} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} |f'(b)| + |f'(x)| \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.4 If we set $\psi(t) = t$ and $\alpha = 1 = s = k$ in Theorem 2.2, then we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \left\{ \frac{v-y_1}{y_2-y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{y_2-v}{y_2-y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \right\} - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \int_{x+a-v}^{x+a-y_1} f(t) dt + \int_{x+b-y_2}^{x+b-v} f(t) dt \right\} \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (|f'(x)| + |f'(a)|) - \left[\frac{1}{3} |f'(y_1)| + \frac{1}{6} |f'(v)| \right] \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (|f'(x)| + |f'(b)|) - \left[\frac{1}{3} |f'(y_2)| + \frac{1}{6} |f'(v)| \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.5 In Theorem 2.2 with $k = 1$ and $|f'| \leq M$, we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 &\leq \frac{M}{(y_2-y_1)^{(\alpha+1)}} \{ (v-y_1)^{\alpha+1} + (y_2-v)^{\alpha+1} \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The result can be obtained by using $|f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| \leq M$ and $|f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| \leq M$.

Theorem 2.6 We assume that all the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'|^q$ is a s -convex function on $[a, b], q > 1$ then for all $\alpha > 0$, the following inequality satisfies for $t \in [0, 1]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|\Xi_{\alpha, \psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 &\leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha p+k} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha p+k}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + \right. \\
 |f'(b)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} & \left. [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}, \quad (2.6) \\
 \text{where } \frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} & = 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Suppose that $p > 1$. From (2.1), by using the well-known Holder integral inequality and the convexity of $|f'|^q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| dt \\
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| dt \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{\alpha p}{k}} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])|^q dt\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{\alpha p}{k}} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])|^q dt\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{\alpha p}{k}} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_0^1 \{|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_1)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q]\} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{\alpha p}{k}} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_0^1 \{|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_2)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q]\} dt\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha p+k}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + \right. \\
 & |f'(a)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \left. \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha p+k}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + \right. \\
 & |f'(b)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \left. \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}},
 \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof.

Corollary 2.7 *If we set $\psi(t) = t, y_1 = a, y_2 = b$ and $v = x$ with $\alpha = 1 = k = s$ in Theorem 2.6, then we have the following inequality*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| f(x) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2^{\frac{1}{q}}(b-a)} \left(\frac{1}{p+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times \left[(x-a)^2 \{|f'(a)|^q + |f'(x)|^q\}^{\frac{1}{q}} + \right. \\
 & \left. (b-x)^2 \{|f'(b)|^q + |f'(x)|^q\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.8 *If we set $\psi(t) = t$ and $\alpha = 1 = s = k$ in Theorem 2.6, then we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left\{ \frac{v-y_1}{y_2-y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{y_2-v}{y_2-y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \right\} \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \int_{x+a-v}^{x+a-y_1} f(t) dt + \int_{x+b-y_2}^{x+b-v} f(t) dt \right\} \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{p+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{1}{2} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{p+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ |f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - \right. \\
 & \left. \frac{1}{2} [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.9 *In Theorem 2.6 with $|f'| \leq M$ and $s = 1 = k$, we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \leq \\
 & \frac{M}{(y_2-y_1)} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha p+1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \{(v-y_1)^{\alpha+1} + (y_2-v)^{\alpha+1}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The result can be demonstrated by using $|f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| \leq M$ and $|f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| \leq M$.

Theorem 2.10 *We assume that all the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'|^q$ is a s -convex function on $[a, b], q \geq 1$, then for all $\alpha > 0$, the following inequality*

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\
 & \leq \frac{k(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha+k}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q) - \right. \\
 & \left. \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_1)|^q + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} + \\
 & \frac{k(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha+k}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q) \right. \\
 & \left. - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_2)|^q + \beta_k(\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}},
 \end{aligned}$$

satisfy for $t \in [0, 1]$, where $p^{-1} + q^{-1} = 1$.

Proof. Suppose that $q \geq 1$. From (2.1), by using the power-mean integral inequality and the convexity of $|f'|^q$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a-[ty_1+(1-t)v])|^q dt \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b-[ty_2+(1-t)v])|^q dt \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 (t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} dt)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a-[ty_1+(1-t)v])|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 (t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} dt)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b-[ty_2+(1-t)v])|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 (t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} dt)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left(\int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \{ |f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_1)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q] \} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 (t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} dt)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left(\int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \{ |f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_2)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q] \} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \leq \frac{k(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha+k} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_1)|^q + \beta_k (\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \frac{k(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{k}{\alpha+k} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha+k} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q) - \left[\frac{1}{\alpha+sk+k} |f'(y_2)|^q + \beta_k (\alpha+k, ks+k) |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

Which ends the proof.

Corollary 2.11 *If we set $\psi(t) = t, y_1 = a, y_2 = b$ and $v = x$ with $\alpha = 1 = k = s$ in Theorem 2.10, then we have the following inequality*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| f(x) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{3(b-a)} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[(x-a)^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} |f'(a)|^q + |f'(x)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} + (b-x)^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} |f'(b)|^q + |f'(x)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.12 *If we set $\psi(t) = t$ and $\alpha = 1 = s = k$ in Theorem 2.10, then we have the following Ostrowski- Mercer inequality*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left\{ \frac{v-y_1}{y_2-y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{y_2-v}{y_2-y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \int_{x+a-v}^{x+a-y_1} f(t) dt + \int_{x+b-y_2}^{x+b-v} f(t) dt \right\} \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q) - \left[\frac{1}{3} |f'(y_1)|^q + \frac{1}{6} |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q) - \left[\frac{1}{3} |f'(y_2)|^q + \frac{1}{6} |f'(v)|^q \right] \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.13 *In Theorem 2.10 with $|f'| \leq M$ and $s = 1 = k$, we have the following Ostrowski- Mercer inequality*

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \leq \frac{M}{(y_2-y_1)(\alpha+1)} \{ (v-y_1)^{\alpha+1} + (y_2-v)^{\alpha+1} \}.$$

Proof. The result can be demonstrated by using $|f'(x+a-[ty_1+(1-t)v])| \leq M$ and $|f'(x+b-[ty_2+(1-t)v])| \leq M$.

Theorem 2.14 *We assume that all the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'|^q$ is a s -convex function on $[a, b], q > 1$, then for all $\alpha > 0$, the following inequality satisfies for $t \in [0, 1]$, where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.*

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \tag{2.7} \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{k}{p(\alpha p+k)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q) - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\} \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{k}{p(\alpha p+k)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q) - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From (2.1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & |\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a-[ty_1+(1-t)v])|^q dt \\ & \quad + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k+1}}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b-[ty_2+(1-t)v])|^q dt. \end{aligned}$$

By using the Young's inequality as

$$uv < \frac{1}{p} u^p + \frac{1}{q} v^q$$

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)|$$

$$\leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt + \frac{1}{q} \int_0^1 |f'(x + a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \right\} \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt + \frac{1}{q} \int_0^1 |f'(x + b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \right\}.$$

By the convexity of $|f'|^q$, we have

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\ \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \\ \times \left\{ \frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt + \frac{1}{q} \int_0^1 \{|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_1)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q] \} dt \right\} \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \\ \times \left\{ \frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt + \frac{1}{q} \int_0^1 \{|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - [t^s |f'(y_2)|^q + (1-t)^s |f'(v)|^q] \} dt \right\} \\ \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{k}{p(ap+k)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q]) \right\} \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{k}{p(ap+k)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - \frac{1}{s+1} [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q]) \right\}.$$

Which ends the proof.

Corollary 2.15 If we choose $\psi(t) = t$ and $\alpha = k = s = 1$ in Theorem 2.14, we have the following Mercer-Ostrowski inequality

$$\left| \left\{ \frac{v-y_1}{y_2-y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{y_2-v}{y_2-y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \right\} - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \int_{x+a-v}^{x+a-y_1} f(t) dt + \int_{x+b-y_2}^{x+b-v} f(t) dt \right\} \right| \\ \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{p(p+1)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(a)|^q - \frac{1}{2} [|f'(y_1)|^q + |f'(v)|^q]) \right\} \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{p(p+1)} + \frac{1}{q} (|f'(x)|^q + |f'(b)|^q - \frac{1}{2} [|f'(y_2)|^q + |f'(v)|^q]) \right\}.$$

Corollary 2.16 In Theorem 2.14 with $k = 1$ and $|f'| \leq M$, we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \leq \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \frac{1}{(ap+1)p + \frac{1}{q} M^q} \right\} [(v-y_1)^{\alpha+1} + (y_2-v)^{\alpha+1}].$$

Theorem 2.17 We assume that all the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'|^q$ is s -concave function on

$[a, b]$, $q > 1$, then for all $\alpha > 0$, the following inequality satisfies for $t \in [0, 1]$, where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\ \leq \left(\frac{k}{ap+k} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ \times \left\{ \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left| f' \left(x + a - \frac{y_1+v}{2} \right) \right| + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \left| f' \left(x + b - \frac{y_2+v}{2} \right) \right| \right\}. \tag{2.8}$$

Proof. From (2.1), by using the Holder inequality, we obtain

$$|\Xi_{\alpha,\psi} f(y_1, y_2, x, v)| \\ \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])| dt \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])| dt \\ \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ + \frac{(y_2-v)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}+1}}{y_2-y_1} \int_0^1 \left(t^{\frac{ap}{k}} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}. \tag{2.9}$$

Since $|f'|^q$ is concave mapping, therefore from (1.1), we obtain

$$\int_0^1 |f'(x+a - [ty_1 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \leq \left| f' \left(x + a - \frac{y_1+v}{2} \right) \right|^q, \tag{2.10}$$

and

$$\int_0^1 |f'(x+b - [ty_2 + (1-t)v])|^q dt \leq \left| f' \left(x + b - \frac{y_2+v}{2} \right) \right|^q. \tag{2.11}$$

We obtain the following inequality (2.8) by placing the inequality (2.10) and (2.11) in (2.9). Which ends the proof.

Remark If we set $\psi(t) = t$, $y_1 = a$, $y_2 = b$, $v = x$ and $\alpha = 1 = k$ in Theorem 2.17, then it reduces to Theorem 5 in [?] yields the same result with $s = 1$.

Corollary 2.18 If we choose $\psi(t) = t$ and $\alpha = k = 1$ in Theorem 2.17, we have the following Ostrowski-Mercer inequality

$$\left| \left\{ \frac{v-y_1}{y_2-y_1} f(x+a-y_1) + \frac{y_2-v}{y_2-y_1} f(x+b-y_2) \right\} - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ \int_{x+a-v}^{x+a-y_1} f(t) dt + \int_{x+b-y_2}^{x+b-v} f(t) dt \right\} \right| \\ \leq \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left| f' \left(x + a - \frac{y_1+v}{2} \right) \right| + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left| f' \left(x + \right. \right. \right.$$

$$b - \frac{y_2+v}{2} \Bigg\}.$$

Applications

Consider the following two special means for $d_1 \neq d_2$, with $0 < d_1 < d_2$.

The arithmetic means:

$$A(d_1, d_2) = \frac{d_1+d_2}{2}.$$

The generalized logarithmic mean:

$$L_m(d_1, d_2) = \left[\frac{d_2^{m+1} - d_1^{m+1}}{(m+1)(d_2 - d_1)} \right]^{\frac{1}{m}}; m \in \mathbb{R} - \{-1, 0\}.$$

Proposition 3.1 Suppose $a, b > 0$, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ \frac{n(v-y_1)}{(y_2-y_1)(r+2n)} (2A(x, a) - y_1)^{\frac{r}{n}+2} \right\} + \\ & \left\{ \frac{n(y_2-v)}{(y_2-y_1)(r+2n)} (2A(x, b) - y_2)^{\frac{r}{n}+2} \right\} \\ & - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ (v-y_1) L_{\frac{r}{n}+1}^{\frac{r}{n}+1}(x+a-y_1, x+a-v) + (y_2-v) L_{\frac{r}{n}+1}^{\frac{r}{n}+1}(x+b-y_2, x+b-v) \right\} \\ & \leq \\ & \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ A \left(|x|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |a|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{3} |y_1|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} + \frac{1}{6} |v|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ A \left(|x|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |b|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{3} |y_2|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} + \frac{1}{6} |v|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The result can be obtained immediately from Corollary 2.12 by considering the convex function $f(x) = \frac{n}{r+2n} x^{\frac{r}{n}+2}, x > 0$.

Proposition 3.2 Suppose $a, b > 0$, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ \frac{n(v-y_1)}{(y_2-y_1)(r+2n)} (2A(x, a) - y_1)^{\frac{r}{n}+2} \right\} + \\ & \left\{ \frac{n(y_2-v)}{(y_2-y_1)(r+2n)} (2A(x, b) - y_2)^{\frac{r}{n}+2} \right\} \\ & - \frac{1}{y_2-y_1} \left\{ (v-y_1) L_{\frac{r}{n}+1}^{\frac{r}{n}+1}(x+a-y_1, x+a-v) + (y_2-v) L_{\frac{r}{n}+1}^{\frac{r}{n}+1}(x+b-y_2, x+b-v) \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{(v-y_1)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left[\frac{1}{p(p+1)} + \frac{1}{q} \left\{ 2A \left(|x|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |a|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) - A \left(|y_1|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |v|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) \right\} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \frac{(y_2-v)^2}{y_2-y_1} \left[\frac{1}{p(p+1)} + \frac{1}{q} \left\{ 2A \left(|x|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |b|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) - A \left(|y_2|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q}, |v|^{\left(\frac{r}{n}-1\right)q} \right) \right\} \right].$$

Proof. The result can be obtained immediately from Corollary 2.15 by considering the convex function $f(x) = \frac{n}{r+2n} x^{\frac{r}{n}+2}, x > 0$.

4. Conclusion

In this paper, we have presented some new general fractional bounds for Ostrowski-Mercer inequality through k -unified fractional operators based on monotone mapping and Breckner convexity. From our proposed results several interesting and novel special cases can be extracted. For different substitutions of monotone mapping ψ , we obtain the various fractional versions of Ostrowski's like inequalities for Breckner s -convex mapping. These results are fruitful in estimating the left side of Hermite-Hadamard Mercer-type inequalities. In the future, we will try to investigate the error terms of Newton-Cote schemes via Mercer inequality and generalized proportional fractional operators.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

If the study does not require an Ethics Approval, the following declaration can be used:

“The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.”

Otherwise, please declare the board name granting ethics approval, approval date and approval number.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendices

If there is more than one appendix, they should be entitled as A, B, etc. Equations in appendices should have separate numbers: Eq. (A.1), Eq. (A.2), etc. Tables and figures in appendices should be numbered as Table A.1 and Figure A.1, etc., respectively.

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